

LINGUISTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF DIPLOMATIC CORRESPONDENCE

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Abstract. *Linguistic features of diplomatic correspondence, their study in linguistics and their importance in formal style are highlighted in the structure of formal style.*

The methods of description, comparison, contrast, generalization, and integral analysis were used to illuminate the research topic.

Linguistic features of official working documents and diplomatic correspondence texts on official speech are proved by examples.

The scientific significance of the results of the work is determined by filling and expanding the scientific and theoretical views related to the research of the theoretical issues of methodology, in particular, the problems related to the linguistic features of diplomatic documentation and correspondence. The practical importance of the work is that it can be used as a theoretical resource in the preparation of educational textbooks, in passing such subjects as speech culture, linguistic analysis of the official text.

Keywords: *formal style, formal speech, diplomatic expressions, diplomatic document, linguistics, syntactic features, synonymous series, interrogative and exclamatory sentences.*

INTRODUCTION. Throughout our life, we use different styles, sometimes artistic style, sometimes scientific style, but the style we use most in communication is conversational style. In fact, every person should know not only the style of everyday conversation, but also the style of official business. Because everyone who is related to social life, whether it is a doctor, teacher, driver, has to write an application, a receipt or a biography, even an invitation has to be written properly. It shows respect and attention to the person or persons to whom writing is offered.

The historical naming of official documents also differed from today's official business documents: "In the early and middle ages, there were many types of documents used in court practice, diplomatic relations, notarial relations between people, and other legal fields. They are recorded in official documents from those times, historical and artistic works with terms such as yarlıg, nišan, bitim, bildırgülük, bitig, baş bitig, ata bitig, bodum bitig, ötug bitig, ay bitig, bişuğ, yumuş, bictas bitig, tutsuğ. done" [5; 12].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Another important type of official speech is diplomatic and commercial correspondence. It is necessary to correctly choose this type of document based on its content, to fully and precisely follow the rules of writing, and to take into account the traditions of the country sending the document. Any type of diplomatic documents sent must be answered with the same type. Diplomatic correspondence is conducted by foreign ministries in the official language of the country and a translation in an international language is attached. Embassies can also conduct correspondence in their national languages or in the language of the country where they are located.

Russian linguist M.N. Kozhina distinguishes diplomatic relations as a separate style: "Diplomatic relations and the sphere of communication are very controversial and not supported by many authors, so the diplomatic style can be distinguished"[2;275].

It is necessary to pay attention to words in diplomatic documents. Their language should be simple, fluent, free of idioms, and expressions like "half a cup at the bottom of the cup" should not be used. Words of praise are one of the necessary parts of notes and statements, which are the most basic type of diplomatic correspondence. The frequent use of respectful words such as "Dear Sir", "Your Excellency", "I assure you of my high regard for you" gives it a friendly tone, and its less use gives it a formal tone.

"President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

To His Excellency Shavkat Mirziyoyev

His Excellency the President,

my dear brother,

On the occasion of the Independence Day of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I congratulate you, Your Excellency, and the entire Uzbek people with my most sincere feelings on behalf of my people and myself.

The friendly and fraternal Republic of Uzbekistan is contributing to the stability and peace of the region by increasing its prosperity and stability under the influence of the reforms carried out under the leadership of Your Excellency.

Turkey and the Turkish people will continue to stand shoulder-to-shoulder today and tomorrow in these efforts of Uzbekistan and its Uzbek brothers.

Together with Your Excellency, we have raised the strategic partnership based on strong brotherly ties between our countries to an unprecedented level in a short period of time. I am very pleased to see that there is a strong will to maintain this level and to raise it to greater heights.

Taking this opportunity, I wish you, Your Excellency, health and happiness, well-being and safety to our friend and brother Uzbek people.

Recep Tayyip Erdogan

The President of the Republic of Turkey ("People's Word" newspaper. September 1, 2021 issue).

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Interrogative and exclamatory sentences are almost never used in official documents, mainly indicative and imperative sentences are used.

"Official-departmental speech style is a style that serves social-legal relations in society, state and inter-state official, political-economic, cultural relations. This method is distinguished by its documentary character. Accordingly, this type of written speech related to service is the style of state laws, decrees, statements, contracts, office documents, announcements and other official correspondence" [4; 119].

CONCLUSION. Today, while our government has opened wide opportunities for the development of the state language, a wide path has been opened for the development of perfect official documentation in Uzbek. In addition, it was established that the official working documents should be fully aware of the laws and regulations and that every enterprise, organization and institution, as well as persons related to the society in general, should keep them in the prescribed manner. Therefore, it is necessary for a modern leader to be able to easily express any necessary information in the appropriate forms of the language of official documents, and to have excellent skills in departmental work.

Documentary expert A.S. Golovach said: "One of the main reasons for the shortcomings in the field of management is the lack of theoretical and practical training in the majority of employees in the same field, they do not have enough guidelines, methods and ways of working with documents accepted in institutions, organizations and enterprises. they don't know enough".[3;3] This, of course, can cause various problematic situations. It is always beneficial for anyone to have complete information about official documents.

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